

**PHYSICAL-MOTOR DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6639962>

Abstract. *Physical development is the growth and change that occurs in a person's body. The most obvious changes are changes in body shape and size. Meanwhile, motor development is the development of all forms of changes that occur progressively in a child's ability to be able to perform various movements obtained through the interaction between maturity factors and training or experience during life which can be seen through changes/movements made. In the learning process, it appears that student activities are very diverse. Starting from how they move, socialize, act, and interact with friends around them. Then from the skills of teachers in developing children's creativity so that they can produce children who have physical motor development who can adapt to the classroom environment, school, and outside of school. All these activities are positive so that they will be able to form and produce students who have great personalities, are intelligent, skilled, capable, creative, and have noble character. Suggestions for elementary school teachers are that it is necessary to provide learning that will foster students' interest in creating according to their imagination. As well as teachers can develop new media which will later be able to stimulate the physical-motor activities of students in the learning process. In the future, research is also needed to support the physical-motor development of elementary school children.*

Keywords: *Development, Physical Motor, Elementary School Age Children, Development, Physical Motor, Elementary School Age Children*

ФИЗИКО-ДВИГАТЕЛЬНОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ У ДЕТЕЙ В НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЕ

Аннотация. *Физическое развитие - это рост и изменения, происходящие в теле человека. Наиболее очевидные изменения - это изменения в форме и размере тела. Между тем, двигательное развитие - это развитие всех форм изменений, которые постепенно происходят в способности ребенка выполнять различные движения, полученные в результате взаимодействия факторов зрелости и обучения или опыта в течение жизни, которые можно увидеть через сделанные изменения / движения. В процессе обучения оказывается, что деятельность учащихся очень разнообразна. Начиная с того, как они двигаются, общаются, ведут себя и взаимодействуют с окружающими их друзьями. Затем от навыков учителей в развитии детского творчества, чтобы они могли производить детей с физическим моторным развитием, которые могут адаптироваться к классной среде, школе и вне школы. Все эти мероприятия носят позитивный характер, так что они смогут формировать и выпускать студентов, обладающих выдающимися личностями, умных, квалифицированных, способных, творческих и талантливых.*

Ключевые слова: *развитие, двигательная активность, дети младшего школьного возраста, развитие, двигательная активность, дети младшего школьного возраста.*

INTRODUCTION

Education is the process of changing the attitude and behavior of a person or group of people to mature humans through teaching and training efforts. From an early age, humans need education in the process of developing it into play. The average age of Uzbek children when they enter primary school is 6 years and finish (graduate) at 12 years of age. When referring to the division of stages of child development, school-age children are in two stages of development, the first is middle childhood (6-9 years), and the second is late childhood (10-12 years).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Children of primary school age have different characteristics from younger children. He likes to play, likes to move, likes to work in groups, and likes to feel or do something directly. Therefore, teachers should develop a learning process that links play with lessons, then teachers can also get children to move or move, children are also taught how to work or learn in groups, and teachers provide opportunities to be directly involved in learning. Understanding of children is the beginning of success in education. The world of children is a world of the play, when they play, children will absorb everything that happens in their surroundings, that play is also an essential requirement and needs for elementary school children, through playing activities children will be able to achieve the demands and needs of dimensional development from the motor, cognitive, creativity, language, emotion, social, values, and attitude to life. The aspect of motor development is one aspect of development that can integrate the development of other aspects. Motoric physical development is defined as the development of the elements of maturity and controlling body movements. Physical development has a very important role in children's lives, either directly or indirectly. Directly a child's physical development will determine the child's skills in movement. While indirectly, physical growth and development will affect how children perceive themselves and how children perceive others, physical development goes hand in hand with motor development. Impaired motor physical development at the age of elementary school children becomes a separate obstacle in their activities, among others, children will have difficulty playing, writing, erasing the blackboard, and so on.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical Development of Children's Elementary School Humans consist of physical and psychological, physical is the place for the development of various developments in humans. In the physical, there is always cognitive, social, moral, religious, and language development. Human physical development in several stages, starting from childhood, adolescence, adulthood, and old age. A change that stands out and is visible in the individual is physical.

The physical or the body is a very amazing and complex organ system. Broadly speaking, the physical growth and development of students can be divided into three stages, namely the stage after birth to three years of age, then the stage of

children to pre-puberty (3-10 years), puberty stage (10-14 years), and stage adolescents (12 years of age and over) Individual physical development includes four aspects, namely the nervous system, muscles, endocrine glands and the physical structure / body. For school-age children and adolescents, optimal physical growth and development is very important, because the physical growth and development of children will directly or indirectly affect their daily behavior Directly the physical growth of the child will determine the child's skills in movement. Meanwhile, indirectly, physical growth and development will affect the way children see

themselves and others. This will be seen from the general adjustment patterns of children when they are around them.

Based on previous research, that there are 3 physical differences in children, including there are children whose body growth is greater than other children, there are also children whose body growth is slower where their bodies are smaller than others, then there are some children who have a normal height which is equivalent and by growth in their age. Their activities can also be seen in class. Children who have large bodies feel that they can lead their other friends, they seem happy to tell their friends to get the things they need, then these smaller children have an extraordinary activity where they can't just sit quietly doing tasks at the table each but they often go around and observe their other friends. Also, children who have a comparable body have different activities, some are writing, some are teaching their friends and some are chatting while doing assignments.

Motoric Development of Children's Elementary School At school age, children's motor development is smoother, more perfect, and well-coordinated, as the child increases in weight and strength. Children seem to be able to control and coordinate the movements of their limbs such as moving their arms and legs well. The muscles in his arms and legs have started to get stronger so that various physical activities such as kicking, jumping, throwing, catching, and running can be done more accurately and quickly. Besides, children are also increasingly able to maintain their body balance. Mastery of the body, such as crouching, doing various gymnastics, and sporting activities, is growing rapidly. They also begin to display the complex, intricate, and rapid movements needed to produce good quality craftwork or to play certain musical instruments. To refine their motor skills the children continue to do various physical activities. This physical activity is carried out in the form of games that are sometimes informal in nature, games that are governed by children themselves, such as the game of hide-and-seek, where children use their motor skills, besides, children also involve themselves in formal sports game activities, such as gymnastics, swimming, or playing hockey. Based on previous research, It appears that the better the physical development of the child's motor skills, the more able the child is to control himself to make body movements that can be coordinated well. For example, when an outsider enters their class while the learning process is ongoing, these elementary school students have a high level of awareness of new people and can coordinate their body movements well, namely by showing high respect by bowing their heads and smiling. with friendly.

Elementary School Children Learning Development Stage The stage of the development of the learning behavior of elementary school students is very much based on aspects of themselves and the environment around them. Both of these things are not possible because the learning process is in the context of students' interactions with their environment. The interaction then forms a good habit that will continue to be carried out as an effort to habituate oneself. Children at school age (7-11 years) are at a concrete operational stage In this age range, the visible behavior of the child is that the child begins to look at the world objectively, shifts from one situation to another, then the child also starts thinking operationally as evidenced by the child being able to classify objects around him.

Where also in this phase the child is smart in understanding the concepts of substance, length, width, area, height, low, light, and weight. The learning tendency of elementary school

children has three characteristics, namely concrete, integrative and, hierarchical. Concrete in the learning process contains meaning that can be seen, heard, smelled, touched, and tampered with, with an emphasis on the use of the environment as a learning resource that can be optimized to achieve quality, meaningful and valuable learning processes and outcomes. In essence, elementary school children have not been able to sort out concepts from various disciplines, this shows a deductive way of thinking, namely from general things to specific things

Physical-Motoric Development of Elementary School Children Physical development is the growth and change that occurs in a person's body. The most visible changes are changes in body shape and size. While motor development is the development of all forms of changes that occur progressively in a child's ability to be able to perform various movements obtained through the interaction between maturity factors and training or experience (experience) during life which can be seen through changes/movements made. So that to refine motor skills, children continue to do various physical activities. This physical activity is carried out in the form of games that are sometimes informal in nature, games that are regulated by the child, such as the game of hide-and-seek, where children use their motor skills, besides, children also involve themselves in physical activities, games, and sports.

Based on previous research It is explained that their physical motor development in the learning process, there are 5 groups of child development, namely: 1) the first group, namely children who have been seen entering puberty where they have started to be able to take care of themselves then in terms of their movements are very guarded so that they look handsome and neat; 2) For the second group are children who prefer to play rather than learn which is seen when in the learning process they listen but still play while whispering with a friend beside them and then fall asleep without feeling that they are learning; 3) For the third group, children who are indeed shy, rarely move, they just sit quietly while listening to the teacher explain the lesson and when the teacher asks them if they understand the material presented they just shut up and look down; 4) Also for the fourth group of children, namely the group of children sitting in front, they are children who can be categorized as children who excel in class, we can see that when the teacher asks enthusiastically they raise their hands and answer questions well; 5) For the last group, namely the group of children who have the ability to receive lessons very slowly from other friends, when the researcher observes the learning process it appears that there are children who look forward but it appears that there is no response to body or eye movements which indicate that the child understands what the teacher conveyed their blank stares as if looking forward but not paying attention.

CONCLUSIONS

Physical development is the growth and change that occurs in the body someone. The most obvious changes are changes in the shape and size body. While motor development is the development of all forms of changes that occur progressively in the ability of children to be able to do various movements obtained through the interaction between factors of maturation and training or experiences during life that can be seen through changes/movements made. In the learning process, it appears that student activities are very diverse. Starting from how they move, socialize, act, and interact with friends around them. Then from the skills of teachers in developing children's creativity so that they can produce children who have physical motor development who can adapt to the classroom environment, school, and outside of school. All

these activities are positive so that they will be able to form and produce students who have great personalities, are intelligent, skilled, capable, creative, and have noble character. Suggestions for elementary school teachers are that it is necessary to provide learning that will foster students' interest in creating according to their imagination. As well as teachers can develop new media which will later be able to stimulate the physical-motor activities of students in the learning process. In the future, research is also needed to support the physical-motor development of elementary school children.

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